

The classification affiliation of the first dictionaries in Besermyan

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Summary: The status and classification of the Besermyan language, spoken by the northwest Udmurt Republic's Cheptsya River residents, demand further investigation. The literature presents conflicting views, referring to it as a dialect or subdialect of Udmurt or a distinct language. The origin of Besermyan also sparks debate. While most contemporary linguists view it as a Udmurt dialect, others, like Y. Wichmann, suggest that the Besermyans are Tatars who assimilated into Udmurt culture.

Studies examining the lexical and phonetic distinctions between contemporary Besermyan dialects and literary Udmurt, as well as other Udmurt dialects, have revealed that the core vocabulary of Besermyan is remarkably similar to literary Udmurt (94% of words from the 100-word Swadesh list coincide with each other). However, significant phonetic variations have been identified between Besermyan dictionaries and the audio dictionaries of Udmurt dialects.

To comprehend what constitutes innovation—whether it's the similarity in vocabulary or the differences in phonetics—this article will first examine the earliest Besermyan dictionaries, compiled in the 19th century, from the viewpoint of their graphics and lexical variations compared to dictionaries and concordances of other dialects created during the same era. Subsequently, the morphological dictionaries of Besermyan and other contemporary Udmurt dialects, as well as the literary language, will be analyzed, as morphology is thought to most accurately capture archaic similarities and differences.

The graphical analysis of the earliest Besermyan dictionaries shows that in the 19th century, Besermyan was even closer to the northern and central Udmurt dialects than to the southern ones. A comparison of morphological affixes has also confirmed this conclusion. The innovative phonetic features of modern Besermyan dialects likely emerged over the last 150 years due to contact influences and cannot be used as a basis for the genetic classification of Besermyan.

Keywords: Udmurt dialects, Besermyan, etymology, phonetics, morphology, linguistic platforms, computational statistical analysis methods, genetic language relationship.

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Introduction

The status and classification of the Besermyan language, spoken by the northwest Udmurt Republic's Cheptsya River residents, need further investigation. The literature mentions it as either a dialect or subdialect of Udmurt [Teplyashina 1970: 35; Languages of the Russian Federation and Neighboring States 2005] or a distinct language «List of Languages of the Russian Federation» <https://jazykirf.iling-ran.ru/groups/Permic.shtml>.

There are differing viewpoints on the origin of Besermyan. In philological literature, it is generally considered that Besermyan is

closely related to Udmurt, and, according to most scholars of the 20th century, is a dialect of Udmurt. However, since 1870, experts in other fields have expressed different opinions. For example, in the monograph [Vasilyev, Bekhterev 1870], it is suggested that the Besermyans are a mix of Udmurts, Mari, Tatars, and Bashkirs from the Zakamsk region. [Lavrentyev 1881] notes that "the Besermyans are similar to the Chuvash people and probably arrived with the Tatars." In the monograph [Shestakov 1859], the view is expressed that "the Besermyans are baptized Tatars mixed with Udmurts." A detailed list of opinions from historians, folklorists, and geographers who consider the Besermyans to be an originally Turkic tribe that acquired Permic traits through contact with the

Udmurts can be found in the monograph [Teplishina 1970: 6-21]. Even linguist Y. Wichmann, the first to collect Besermyan word records, believed that the Besermyans were Udmurtized Tatars [Wichmann 1893: 7].

Modern studies of the lexical differences between the Besermyan language and other Udmurt dialects show that Besermyan is not significantly different from other Udmurt dialects. Two Besermyan dialects, whose audio dictionaries were compiled in 2003-2014 in the villages of Shamardan (Yukamensky district) and Vortsa (Yarsky district), have the greatest number of differences from the peripheral-southern dialect (6%), while the percentage of similarity with other dialect groups is even higher [Bezenova, Normanskaja 2022: 135-145]. This indirectly suggests that Besermyan is a Udmurt dialect rather than a separate language, let alone a Turkic one.

However, in the field of phonetics, significant differences have been observed between Besermyan dictionaries and Udmurt dialect audio dictionaries [Bezenova, Normanskaja 2022: 124-147]. Research into phonetic innovations between modern Udmurt dictionaries conducted on the LingvoDoc platform (lingvodoc.ispras.ru) revealed that the Besermyan language has the highest number of changes compared to Proto-Udmurt. For initial consonants, the following shifts are characteristic: 1) *t > tʃ; 2) *č > tɛ; 3) *ʒ > tɛ; 4) *s > ɛ; for medial consonants: 5) *č > tɛ; 6) *ś > ɛ. In the vowel system of the first syllable, the following changes occur: 7) *i > ɐ; 8) *u > u; 9) *u > ɐ; 10) *ə > ɜ; 11) *ɔ > ɜ; 12) *ɐ > i. As shown in [Bezenova, Normanskaja 2022: 124-147], modern Udmurt dialects exhibit far fewer phonetic innovations: 6 in the northern dialect, 10 in the central, 6 in the central-southern, and 8 in the peripheral-southern dialects. In the earliest books from the late 19th century, 3 innovations were noted for the northern dialect, 4 for the central-southern, and 4 for the peripheral-southern dialect.

To address the question of the degree of similarity between Besermyan and Udmurt dialects and the literary Udmurt language, the following analyses can be conducted:

1. Early Besermyan Dictionaries (19th Century): These can be examined to determine whether the phonetic differences between Besermyan and other Udmurt dialects have increased or decreased over time. If the amount of differences decreased, it may suggest a Turkic substrate with gradual influence from the Udmurt language. However, if the differences increased, it is likely that Turkic contacts and linguistic changes occurred later. This is further supported by the fact that borrowings are predominantly found outside the core vocabulary.

2. Etymological Affix Analysis: In addition to phonetic and glottochronological proximity, it would be valuable to assess the number of etymologically related affixes in Besermyan and other Udmurt dialects.

Materials and methods

To address the first task, we selected the two earliest Besermyan dictionaries, referenced in Teplishina's monograph [Teplishina 1970: 38-41], compiled by Y. Wichmann in 1892 and N.P. Steinfeld in 1894. For the purpose of comprehensive comparison with modern dictionaries and concordances of the earliest books written in Udmurt dialects, we created databases from these dictionaries. These databases were made publicly available on the LingvoDoc platform and etymologically linked with other dictionaries of the Udmurt dialects.

On LingvoDoc, using a special author-developed program, "Cognate Analysis of Different Dialects of the Same Language" which simulates the work of an etymologist, the analysis process is automated. Figure 1 shows how any registered user of a Selkup dictionary, who is either its creator or has the necessary rights from the dictionary creator, can open the "Tools" option and select various dictionary analysis features.

Figure 1: Using LingvoDoc tools for dictionary analysis

After selecting the option "Cognate Analysis in Different Dialects of the Same Language," the user is presented with an interface that allows them to choose which dialect dictionaries will be analyzed, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Interface allowing the selection of dictionaries for cognate analysis

In the first stage, the Cognate Analysis program processes each symbol from the transcription to find its correspondences in words from other dialects of the same language, which are etymologically linked to the current dictionary. Specifically:

a) Roots are analyzed based on the premise that the first vowel (or vowel combination) in one dialect corresponds to the first vowel (or vowel combination) in another dialect, the first consonant (or consonant combination) corresponds to the first consonant (or consonant combination), and the second consonant corresponds to the second. The output is a list of correspondences for each pair of idioms. The dictionary author can download this list to review, analyze, and verify the accuracy of transcriptions and etymologies that led to non-standard series of correspondences, and make corrections as needed. The algorithm is then restarted using the revised material.

b) The algorithm assesses whether there are phonemes with two or more correspondences in the second dialect. If two or more phonemes from the current dictionary correspond to a single phoneme in another dialect, the algorithm checks for positional distribution between them that may not have been considered in the first stage. As a result, the system provides a list of correspondences between the two dialects in Excel format, including possible distribution rules.

Thus, on LingvoDoc, the Cognate Analysis program was used in the first stage to analyze graphic-phonetic isoglosses between the Besermyan dictionaries by Y. Wichmann (1892) and N.P. Steinfeld (1894), and the concordances of the earliest books written in Udmurt dialects, and uploaded to LingvoDoc:

- Northern Dialect: Dictionary of the written text "The Law of God: A Picture Book for Little Children. In the Votic Language of the Glazov Dialect," 1912.
- Central Dialect: Concordance of the book "Primer for Votic Children of the Sarapul District," 1882.
- Central-Southern Dialect: Dictionary of the written text "The Life of Saint Theodore: In the Votic Language of the Yelabuga Dialect," 1913.
- Peripheral-Southern Dialect: Dictionary of a written text "Christian Teachings by Saint Tikhon in the Votian Language," 1891; "Ÿґет. Святой Тихон дышетэм вѣч кылъѣс. Christian Teachings by St. Tikhon," 1878.

To address the second task of analyzing the degree of morphological similarity, a comprehensive set of tools has been created on LingvoDoc:

1. Uploading or creating morpheme dictionaries: Dictionaries of morphemes can either be uploaded in Excel format or created directly on LingvoDoc.
2. Creating morphological dictionaries from Text Corpora: Morphological dictionaries can be generated from text corpora available in Elan.
3. Linking cognate affixes: Related affixes in morphological dictionaries can be linked through etymological connections.

4. Specialized program for morphological distance: A specialized program, "Morphological distance" has been developed. This tool evaluates the number of etymologically related affixes between any set of languages or dialects and constructs a proximity graph based on this analysis.

For determining the degree of morphological similarity, dictionaries of inflectional morphemes of the Besermyan dialect (as detailed in [Lykina 2008] <https://lingvodoc.ispras.ru/dictionary/8148/1/perspective/8148/2/view>) and of the literary Udmurt language (created by M.P. Bezenova and available here: <https://lingvodoc.ispras.ru/dictionary/6617/114841/perspective/6617/114845/view>) were used. Affixes in these dictionaries were etymologically linked. The dictionaries were then analyzed using the "Morphological Distance" program, which calculated the number of affixes that are not etymologically related in these dictionaries.

Results and findings:

Etymological and phonetic differences of the Besermyan language from other Udmurt dialects in the 19th century

The following proximity graph of the analyzed idioms was created using LingvoDoc, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Proximity graph of the early Udmurt dictionaries and books on LingvoDoc

The graph shows that two groups of Udmurt dialects are distinguished: Peripheral-Southern dialects: "Угет. Святой Тихон дышетэм з'еч кыльёс. Christian teachings by St. Tikhon" 1878 (No. 4 on the graph), "Christian teachings by Saint Tikhon in the Votic language" (No. 5 on the graph), and all others.

Let's examine in which series of correspondences the Cognate Analysis program identified special reflexes.

Table 1: Series of special correspondences in Udmurt books and dictionaries of the 19th century

Northern Dialect: Dictionary of the written text "The Law of God: A Picture Book for Little Children. In the Votic Language of the Glazov Dialect," 1912	Central Dialect: Concordance of the book "Primer for Votic Children of the Sarapul District," 1882	Central-Southern Dialect: Dictionary of the written text "The Life of Saint Theodore: In the Votic Language of the Yelabuga Dialect," 1913	Peripheral-Southern Dialect: "Ўгер. Святой Тихон дышетэм жеч кыльёс. Christian Teachings by St. Tikhon," 1878	Peripheral-Southern Dialect: Dictionary of a written text "Christian Teachings by Saint Tikhon in the Votian Language," 1891	Besermyan dictionary by Y. Wichmann
ч-	ц-	ч-	ч-	ч-	т'с'-
с-	ς-	с-	ς-	ς-	ś-
й-	й-	й-	ɔb-	ɔb-	j-
ö	ö	ö	ö	ö	ε
у	υ	у	υ	υ	u
у	у	у/(j)	ÿ/у	ÿ	u
о	о	о	о	ö	o

From the table, it's evident that the number of regular phonetic distinctions between the Besermyan language and the Northern, Central, and Central-Southern dialects in the 19th century was even smaller than the one between the Peripheral-Southern dialects and the Northern, Central, and Central-Southern dialects.

Let us analyze the variations that have emerged in the contemporary Besermyan dialects over the past century. Utilizing the Cognate Analysis program, the Besermyan dictionary compiled by Y. Wichmann, along with two contemporary Besermyan audio dictionaries recorded between 2003 and 2014 in the villages of Shamardan (Yukamensky District) and Vortsa (Yarsky District) of the Udmurt Republic, were subjected to analysis. Consequently, the following proximity graph was generated, as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Proximity Graph of Besermyan Dictionaries from the 19th to 21st Centuries on LingvoDoc

The graph shows that the 19th-century Besermyan dictionary by Y. Wichmann (No. 1 on the graph) significantly differs from modern dictionaries, however the contemporary Besermyan dictionaries also differ from each other. Let's examine the changes that have occurred in the series of correspondences over the past 100 years. Below, Table 2 presents the series of correspondences that have differences in one of the Udmurt dictionaries.

Table 2: Special Series of Correspondences in Besermyan Dictionaries from the 19th to 21st Centuries

The dictionary by Y. Wichmann from the 19th century	The dictionary recorded in the Shamardan village, 21st century	The dictionary recorded in the Vortsa village, 21st century
<i>e</i>	<i>e</i>	ϵ
<i>e</i>	<i>e</i>	<i>i</i>
<i>o</i>	<i>o</i>	σ
<i>u</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>u</i>
<i>i</i>	<i>v</i>	<i>v</i>
<i>i</i>	<i>v</i>	<i>u</i>
<i>i</i>	<i>v</i>	<i>i</i>
<i>tʲ</i>	<i>tʃ</i>	<i>tʃ</i>
<i>sʲ</i>	ϵ	ϵ

From Table 4, it is evident that the greatest number of changes occurred in the vowel phoneme system. In the village of Shamardan, few changes were observed: *u* > *u*, *i*, *i* > *v*. In the village of Vortsa, the same changes were recorded except for the transition *i* > *v*, along with additional changes, specific only to Vortsa: *e* > ϵ , *e* > *i*, *o* > σ , *i* > *u*. Both dialects experienced changes in consonants: *tʲ* > *tʃ*, *sʲ* > ϵ .

II. Morphological Differences Between Besermyan and Literary Udmurt

Using the Morphological Distance program to compare the morphological dictionaries of Besermyan and Literary Udmurt, created by M.P. Bezenova, we discovered that almost all inflectional affixes in Literary Udmurt have parallels in Besermyan, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Etymologically Related Affixes in Literary Udmurt and Besermyan

1. Morphological Dictionary of the Besermyan Language (Lyukina N. M. "Features of the Language of Balyezin and Yukamen Besermyans (Comparative Characteristics)," 2008)	2. Morphological Dictionary of the Literary Udmurt Language
-a, -ja (ILL (possessive declension))	-a; -я (ILL (possessive declension))
-a, -ja (INE (possessive declension))	-a; -я (INE (possessive declension))
-a, -ja (ITER)	-a; -я (ITER)
-d (2SG; 2PL)	-д (2SG; 2PL)
-e (IMP.2PL)	-э; -е (IMP.2PL)
-e (PL (negative verb particle))	-e (PL (negative verb particle))
-e (PRS.3SG)	-э; -е (PRS.3SG)
-e, -je (ACC)	-э; -е (ACC)
-e, -je (ILL (simple declension))	-e; -э (ILL (simple declension))
-e, -je, -â (POSS.1SG)	-ы; -е; -э (POSS.1SG)
-ed, -jed, -âd, -t, -d, -tâ, -dâ (POSS.2PL; POSS.2SG)	-ды; -эд; -д; -ед; -т; -ыд; -ты (POSS.2PL; POSS.2SG)
-em, -m (PTCP.PST)	-м; -ем; -эм (PTCP.PST)
-emen, -men (CONV)	-мен; -емен; -эмен (CONV)
-emja, -mja (CONV)	-мъя; -эмъя; -емъя (CONV)
-emân, -mân (PTCP.RES)	-емын; -мын; -эмын (PTCP.RES)
-emâs', -mâs' (CONV)	-эмысь; -емысь; -мысь (CONV)

-es (ACC (possessive declension, PL))	-эс; -еc (ACC (possessive declension, PL))
-es', -jes' (PL (adjective))	-есь; -эсь (PL (adjective))
-et'i (ORD)	-емү; -эмү (ORD)
-et'i, -jet'i, -êt'i, -t'i (PROL)	-тү; -ытү; -эмү; -емү (PROL)
-ez, -jez (ACC (simple declension, SG))	-ез; -эз (ACC (simple declension, SG))
-ez, -jez, -êz, -s, -z, -sê, -zê (POSS.3PL; POSS.3SG)	-ез; -с; -з; -ыз; -сь; -эз; -зы (POSS.3PL; POSS.3SG)
-ez, -jez, -êz, -z, -s (DEM)	-ез; -с; -ыз; -эз; -з (DEM)
-ges (CMP)	-гес (CMP)
-i (1PST (I cnj.))	-и; -й (1PST (I cnj.))
-il'l'am, -l'l'am (2PST (PL))	-иллям; -йллям; -ллям (2PST (PL))
-is', -ês', -s' (PTCP.ACT)	-йсь; -ись; -сь (PTCP.ACT)
-j (1PST (II cnj., 1 g.p.))	-й (1PST (II cnj., 1 g.p.))
-ja (ADV)	-я (ADV)
-ku, -kê (CONV (CVB.SIM))	-ку (CONV (CVB.SIM))
-l'l'a (ITER (II cnj.))	-лля (ITER (II cnj.))
-lan' (APP)	-лань (APP)
-le (IMP.2PL)	-лэ; -елэ; -элэ (IMP.2PL)
-le (PL (negative verb particle))	-элэ; -лэ; -елэ (PL (negative verb particle))
-len (GEN)	-лэн (GEN)
-les', -lês' (ABL)	-лэсь (ABL)
-lo, -o (FUT)	-ё; -ло; -о (FUT)
-lê (DAT)	-лы (DAT)
-lê (ITER (I cnj.))	-лы; -л (ITER (I cnj.))
-m (1PL)	-м (1PL)
-m, -em (2PST (SG))	-ем; -м; -эм (2PST (SG))
-m, -mê (POSS.1SG; POSS.1PL)	-мы; -м (POSS.1SG; POSS.1PL)
-mon (CONV (PTCP.PASS))	-мон (CONV (PTCP.PASS))
-mte (NEG.2PST)	-мтэ (NEG.2PST)
-mte (PTCP (PTCP.NEG))	-мтэ (PTCP (PTCP.NEG))
-nê (INF)	-ны (INF)
-o, -lo (PRS.3PL)	-ло; -ё; -о (PRS.3PL)
-on, -n (PTCP (VN))	-он; -н (PTCP (VN))
-ono, -no (IMPERS)	-оно; -ёно; -но (IMPERS)
-ono, -no (PTCP (DEB))	-ёно; -оно; -но (PTCP (DEB))
-ontem, -ntem (PTCP)	-нтэм; -онтэм (PTCP)
-os, -jos (PL (n.))	-ос; -ёс (PL (n.))
-oz', -joz', -oz'a, -joz'a (TER)	-озя; -озь; -ёзя; -ёзь (TER)
-s'k, -êêk, -êik, -êik, -êk (REFL)	-иськы; -йськ; -иськ; -скы; -ськы; -йськы; -ськ; -ск (REFL)
-s'ko, -is'ko, -êiko, -êiko (PRS)	-ськ; -сько; -йсько; -исько (PRS)
-sa (CONV)	-са (CONV)
-sal (SBJV)	-сал (SBJV)
-tek (ABE)	-тэк (ABE)
-tek (CONV (CVB.NEG))	-тэк (CONV (CVB.NEG))
-tê (ACC (simple declension, PL))	-ты (ACC (simple declension, PL))

-tâ (CAUS)	-m; -мы (CAUS)
-z (3PL; 3SG)	-з (3PL; 3SG)
-ĉĉoz' (CONV (CVB.LIM))	-тозь (CONV (CVB.LIM))
-â (ILL (PL))	-ы (ILL (PL))
-â (PL (глаго.))	-ы (PL (глаго.))
-ân (INE (simple declension))	-ын; -н (INE (simple declension))
-ân, -en, -jen, -ânâ, -enâ, -jenâ (INS)	-ен; -ин; -ены; -эны; -эн; -ины; -ын; -ыны (INS)
-âs', -is' (ELA (simple declension))	-сь; -ысь (ELA (simple declension))
-âs'en, -is'en (EGR)	-ысены; -сен; -сены; -ысен (EGR)
-âs'tâ, -is'tâ (ELA (possessive declension))	-ысьты; -сьты (ELA (possessive declension))

And only one affix in Literary Udmurt does not have parallels in Besermyan: -ыз ACC (simple declension, plural).

In addition to these affixes, Besermyan also has a number of innovative case endings according to [Lyukina 2008].

1. Morphological Dictionary of the Besermyan Language (Lyukina N. M. "Features of the Language of Balyezin and Yukamen Besermyans (Comparative Characteristics)," 2008)
-n'ân (2INE)
-n'e (2ILL)
-n'âs', -n'is' (2ELA)
-n'âs'en, -n'is'en (2EGR)
-n'et'i, -n'it'i (2PROL)
-n'oz' (2TER)

These “secondary” cases in Besermyan and their parallels in Northern Udmurt dialects are meticulously discussed in the article [Maksimov 2018], which also provides a wealth of references to relevant literature. All authors concur that the case-forming *-n'*, which initiates secondary cases in both Northern dialects and Besermyan, originates from the postpositional stem *din'* ‘near, around,’ carrying a general meaning of proximity or approach. Word forms featuring the element *-n'* within case affixes are already evident in dialect texts from the late 19th century. However, as noted by [Tepliyashina 1981: 290], the word *din'* was employed in the specific function in both Northern Udmurt and Besermyan dialects but eventually ceased to be used after the popularisation of new cases.

S.A. Maksimov [Maksimov 2018: 44], in line with other scholars, posits that the emergence of these cases in the Udmurt language was a consequence of late interactions between Udmurt and Komi. However, he refutes the notion that they originated from Proto-Permic, as they exhibit somewhat distinct meanings in Komi-Permyak and Udmurt dialects. The idea of contact is supported by the fact that the number of cases in the Northern Udmurt zone reaches up to 21, while in Komi-Permyak dialects, there are also 17-28 cases, compared to 12-13 cases in Southern Udmurt dialects. Maksimov suggests that this disparity may be attributed to interactions between Southern Udmurts and speakers of Turkic languages.

Consequently, all morphological distinctions between Besermyan dialects and Literary Udmurt are not attributable to interactions with Turkic languages, but rather exhibit parallels in Northern Udmurt dialects and Komi languages.

Conclusion

Graphical analysis of the early Besermyan dictionaries showed that in the 19th century, Besermyan was even closer to the Northern and Central Udmurt dialects than the Southern dialects were. Comparison of morphological affixes also confirmed this conclusion. The innovative phonetic features of contemporary Besermyan dialects evidently emerged over the past 150 years under the influence of interactions, and cannot be used as a basis for the genetic classification of Besermyan.

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List of abbreviations

- 1PST — 1 past tense
- 2PST — 2 past tense
- ABE — abessive
- ABL — ablative
- ACC — acusative
- ADV — adverb
- APP — approximative
- CAUS — causative
- CMP — comparative degree suffix
- CONV — converb

CONV — conversion
CVB — adverbial participle
CVB.LIM — limiting adverbial participle
CVB.SIM — simultaneous adverbial participle
DAT — dative
DEB — debitive
DEM — allocative suffix
EGR — egressive
ELA — elative
FUT — future tense
GEN — genitive
ILL — illative
IMP — imperative mood
IMPERS — impersonal
INE — inessive
INF — infinitive
INS — instrumental case
ITER — iterative
NEG — negation
ORD — numeral
PL — plural
POSS — possessive
PROL — prolative
PRS — present tense
PTCP — participle
PTCP.ACT — active participle
PTCP.PASS — passive past tense participle
PTCP.PST — past tense participle
PTCP.RES — resultative-static participle
REFL — reflexive verb
SBJV — subjunctive mood
SG — singular
TER — terminative
VN — verbal noun
g.p. — grammatical person
cnj. — conjugation
n. — noun

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